

Microanalysis of Peasant Households in the Era of Modernization: Evidence from the Russian Empire

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Abstract

The article presents the results of the econometric analysis of microdata obtained from drawing up the budgets of peasant households in five regions – two European (Novgorod province, Simbirsk province) and three Asian (Ural region, Central Asian and Far Eastern) – in the period from the beginning of the Stolypin reform (1906) to the outbreak of the First World War (1914).

The purpose of the study is to shed light on the question of whether there was an agrarian revolution in pre-revolutionary Russia. The regression analysis of the production function showed that the main factor significantly influencing the output is the amount of land, followed by the number of horses, with number of workers being insignificant. At the same time, it follows from the stochastic boundary model applied to the production function that there are no technologically special differences between the regions, whereas technologies did not differ much from previous centuries. Study of peasant farms' embeddedness in market relations demonstrated that marketability in all the regions was approximately 31-37%.

It is concluded that during the period under study in Russia, the modernization of the agricultural sector was at an initial stage, that is, the processes that could later lead to an agrarian revolution were just beginning.

Keywords

econometric analysis, microdata, peasant's households, marketability, modernization of the agricultural sector

JEL codes: Q12, C31

Introduction

In the second half of the 19th century – early 20th century, Russia witnessed a period of rapid growth accompanied by significant structural changes. Many Russian and foreign researchers have covered the successful modernization in pre-revolutionary Russia (Mironov 2012; Davydov 2016; Gregory 1972). One of their key points was the idea that after the Stolypin reforms, the process of modernization in the agricultural sector intensified, including the formation of market relations such as the establishment of land and labor markets, an increase in land transactions, and growth of hired labor. The intensification of economic incentives related to the development of market institutions resulted in higher efficiency in agriculture, increased labor productivity in the agricultural sector pushing extra labor force out of agriculture, which then migrated to cities, shaping a labor market for the industry.

Similar processes could be observed in England, Germany, and, to a certain extent, in France and many other countries where the transition to market relations started much earlier than in Russia. In various publications this process is commonly referred to as the “agricultural revolution” (Allen 1999; Overton 1996).

This raises the question of whether the agricultural revolution took place in Russia (the result of which should be the growth of labor and land productivity), specifically, at what level were market relations in the agricultural sector and, above all, among peasant stratum (accounting for over 80% of the country population) in Russia before World War I. Which stage of modernization was peasant agriculture at? Was it integrated into market relations?

To solve this research issue, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive analysis of different spheres of peasant household activities related to land, labor, and capital market functioning. In this article we aim to explore some aspects of this issue and contribute to the discussion on modernization in Russia in general and the agricultural sector in particular. Specifically, we will analyze how households were integrated into market relations on the eve of World War I and how they responded to institutional changes after the 1905 revolution.

To address the task at hand, we analyzed microdata received from the compiled budgets of peasant households in five regions during the period after the start of the Stolypin reforms (1906), which intensified the formation of private land ownership among peasants and before World War I (1914).

In previous research, materials from budget surveys were used to study the level of well-being among peasants, the structure of their consumption, differences between peasant households, as well as to identify common patterns in the development of peasant households using data from budget surveys in the provinces of the European part of Russia (Shcherbina 1900; Lenin 1947; Chayanov 1929; Chernomorskiy 1955; Kovalchenko et al. 1988; Field 1989; Johnson 1997; Rozinskaya et al. 2021).

Unlike previous scholars, first, we apply not only budget surveys from the European part provinces, but also from the Urals, Middle Asia and Far East, and, second, we use the data after 1906, when peasants were allowed to take *obshchina* (community) lands in private ownership. Unlike other researchers, we focus on the analysis of the level of technological development of peasant households in the regions under study and integration of those households into market relations. Among scholars who have studied peasant budgets, Kovalchenko was the only one to analyze the marketability of peasant households (in the Voronezh and Penza provinces) using statistical methods. We use data from other regions and also apply both statistical and econometric methods.

The article provides a comprehensive analysis of peasant households in terms of their compliance with the criteria that indicate modernization processes in the agricultural sector. In particular, the study considers such criteria as a clear definition of land ownership rights, increased commercialization of the agricultural sector, and technological changes in the agricultural sector. These criteria are based on the works of English-language authors who have studied the agricultural revolution in European countries (Allen 1992; Allen 1999; Overton 1996; *The Agrarian History of Sweden...* 2011).

The analysis showed that the main indicators characterizing the modernization process demonstrated an extremely low level. Land ownership rights remained vague for most of the peasantry even after the Stolypin agrarian reforms. Technologies did not differ much from previous centuries and were virtually identical in different regions, despite differences in per capita regional income. Marketability in all regions under study was approximately 31–37%, i.e. two-thirds of the produced goods was consumed by peasant households themselves and only a third was sold in the market. This confirmed the low integration of households into market relations. This is also supported by the analysis of peasant consumption, showing a great similarity in the structure of consumption by region: the main part of the income was spent on household expenses and food, with an insignificant part of the budget going towards education and spiritual needs.

The conducted microanalysis generally confirms the results obtained by several domestic and foreign researchers on aggregated data for the European regions of Russia (Clark 1987; Kovalchenko et al. 1988; Leonard 2011; Mironov 2012; Ostrovsky 2013). Our contribution is as follows: first, we tested the hypotheses using econometric analysis, and second, we obtained figures for individual regions, including non-European regions. In addition, our study showed that despite climatic and geographical differences, as well as differences in the level of per capita regional income (Markevich 2019), and different institutional backgrounds (presence/absence of serfdom), there were no fundamental differences between the analyzed criteria in the regions under study.

Therefore, this article not only contributes to the abovementioned discussion, but also explores the following issues: modernization of traditional society, challenges of transitioning to market relations, and level of agricultural development in Russia on the eve of the Revolution.

The article consists of the following three sections: the introduction section, which explains the contribution of discussions this article aims at; the second section is a brief overview of the stages other countries have gone through in the process of the agricultural sector modernization and an analysis of historical experience to define the criteria that need to be met to successfully modernize the agricultural sector; while the third section analyzes the budget survey data to see if Russian peasant households meet the necessary criteria for modernization.

Theoretical and historical context

Scholars usually distinguish certain criteria, based on which one can see that the transition from a traditional society to a society based on economic growth took place (Kuznets and Murphy 1966; Rostow 1960); and the most important stage of the transition is modernization of the agricultural sector. To analyze the issue of agricultural revolution in Russia, we will look at researchers who have discussed the main idea behind the agricultural revolution and its

timing in England and other countries of Northern Europe. Although scholars have different opinions about the beginning and end of the agricultural revolution, there is less disagreement about the mechanism behind it. From their point of view, the process of modernization started with institutional changes that led to a very specific definition of land ownership rights (The Agrarian History... 2011, p. 122). In England, for example, it was the “yeoman revolution” or “crop rotation” revolution (Allen 1992, Overton 1996). Clearly defined land rights encouraged the commercialization of peasant households, resulting, in turn, in more efficient land use, further increasing total factor productivity. This process is known as the agricultural revolution (Allen 1999, p. 217). The main feature and result of this revolution was a significant increase in agricultural output per person (Allen 1999, p. 211).

The most important consequence of the increased labor productivity and output per hectare of land was a decreasing demand for workers in the agricultural sector. By 1800, major North European territories have managed to reduce the amount of labor necessary to produce one hectoliter of grain from 6-8 man-days (which was the standard in the 16th century) to 4-5, while crop yields per hectare increased from 8-10 to 12-15 hectoliters. Since the 16th century, when 50% of the population was involved in grain production, and until 1800, when only 30% of the population was involved in grain production, labor time in agriculture decreased from 75% to about 50% (De Vries 2016, p. 160-161). These modernization processes in the agricultural sector provided the foundation for the Industrial revolution.

In Europe, the redistribution of household production resources was a response to the favorable market conditions. Households shifted from periodic contracts with the market (selling produced goods to increase the variety of consumer goods) to market-oriented production (selling produced goods and labor as the basis of their economy). This conversion happened, primarily, as a reaction to the established market conditions rather than due to enforcement by some institutions (though, they did play a significant role at times). A full-fledged market orientation or dependence on it, in turn, demanded certain changes in household consumer behavior (De Vries 2016).

Thus, among the main criteria for the agricultural revolution, we can name the following ones: a clear definition of land ownership rights, increased agricultural sector commercialization, technological changes in the agricultural sector related to the transition to grass cultivation and crop rotation, along with integration with cattle breeding. These changes, in turn, resulted in higher labor productivity and key changes in living conditions of rural producers, motivating them to become even deeper integrated into market relations.

Preconditions for the agricultural revolution in Russia in the late 19th century were just beginning to take shape. An insufficient level of agricultural development manifested in Russia's response to price drops after the 1870s. Unlike several European countries, where price drops encouraged efficiency growth with specialization in cattle breeding becoming a way to cope with agricultural depression, in Russia they led only to a further increase in land under cultivation. Unlike many other European countries, Russia's agricultural sector growth was achieved by expanding cropland without any increase in efficiency (van Zanden 1991, p. 215-239).

It was related mostly to undefined property rights. In the last quarter of the 19th century in Russia, the state faced a decrease in peasant land allotments (Table 1), caused by their splitting among family members due to intensified population growth after the liberation (Rashin 1956). To solve this issue, several laws were passed. The law of March 18, 1886, prohibited family land splits; the law of June 8, 1893, prohibited private (within a family) redistribution; and common (within a community) redistribution was once in 12 years.

Furthermore, the law of December 14, 1893, limited the right of peasants to separate the allotments they had bought from the community, prohibited to mortgage peasant allotments and limited the renting and selling of allotments only within the community. Therefore, the law abolished Article 165 of the Provision on buy-out of 1861, according to which a peasant could buy out his allotment in advance and separate it from the community. The decree of 1906 is the only one that allowed peasants to transfer the cultivated land into their ownership and leave the community¹.

Table 1. Average allotment per male peasant by region

Region	Average allotment (dessiatina = 1.09 hectare per capita)		
	1860	1880	1900
North	7.6	6.1	4.7
East-north	8.1	6.1	4.6
East	9.5	6.5	4.8
Middle Volga	4.0	3.1	2.4
South-East	8.4	5.2	3.5
Middle agricultural (south-east group)	4.1	3.1	2.2
Middle agricultural (south-west group)	3.0	2.2	1.7
Middle industrial	4.0	3.3	2.6
Baltic	3.7	2.9	2.4
North-west	5.0	3.3	2.2
South-west	2.9	2.1	1.4
Little Russia	3.3	2.5	1.7
New Russia	6.2	4.0	2.5
The average for 50 provinces of European Russia	4.8	3.5	2.6

Source: Rubakin NA (1912) *Rossiya v cifrah*. Strana. Narod. Sosloviya. Klassy: Opyt statisticheskoy karakteristiki soslovno-klassovogo sostava naseleniya russkogo gosudarstva [Russia in numbers. A country. People. Estates. Classes: An experience of statistical characteristics of the estate-class composition of the population of the Russian state] Izd-vo "Vestnik znaniya. St. Peterburg.

The efficiency growth was slowed down not only by the lack of clear peasant rights for land, but also by a low commercialization of the agricultural sector. Van Zanden distinguishes the following characteristics to define commercialization of agriculture: the level of urbanization, GDP per capita and cattle per hectare (van Zanden 1991, p. 225). On all these criteria, Russia was lagging behind not only the leading countries in Europe and the U.S., but also countries that were in transition from a traditional society to an economy of growth, such as Sweden (The Agrarian History... 2011, p. 125).

¹ Legally, the right of peasants to buy out land in their ownership has existed since the early 19th century. On December 12, 1801, a decree was issued granting all free citizens the right to purchase immovable property without peasants outside cities (*Polnoe sobranie zakonov Rossijskoj imperii. Sobranie Pervoe* [Complete Collection of Laws of the Russian Empire. First Part] (1889) Vol. 26 № 20.075. S-Petersburg).

It is worth mentioning that commercialization of the agricultural sector could have been facilitated by landlord households, but unlike other European countries (Byres 2009), in Russia, the amount of grain produced by landlord households decreased: the percentage of sown land on privately owned lands in 50 provinces almost halved, from 21.9% to 11.3% (Kovalchenko et al. 1982, p. 215). Proceeding from the mentioned above, we can conclude that without peasant households integrating into market relations, the growth of efficiency in the agricultural sector was considerably complicated.

In the late 19th – early 20th centuries, Russia saw serious changes. The railroad network expanded, the financial system developed, and the migration from rural areas to cities increased. The economy grew at a rapid pace, encouraging the growth of purchasing power, including for agricultural products. The literacy rate was on the rise, etc. Against this background, the Stolypin agrarian reforms were carried out with the aim of establishing a land market, creating middle class, increasing efficiency by consolidating separate land strips into single allotments (canceling strip farming), clearly defining land property rights, that is, creating incentives to increase labor efficiency. How strong was the impact of these changes on the most numerous social strata of the Russian Empire by the beginning of World War I? How far did peasants progress on the way towards modernization? Can it be called an agricultural revolution?

To answer these questions, we have analyzed the microdata received while compiling budgets of peasant households in five regions during the period between the introduction of the Stolypin reforms and the beginning of World War I.

Data sources

This study used microdata from five regions of the Russian Empire, in particular, the budget data of households in the Simbirsk province, Novgorod province, Amur *oblast* (region), Kustanaisk district of the Tugaisk *oblast*, Ural district of Ural *oblast*, Aktyubinsk district of the Turgay *oblast* of the Governor-Generalship of the Steppes, Tchickment district of the Syr-Darya *oblast*.

Before analyzing data from the above-mentioned regions, it is important to compare basic characteristics of these regions to better understand the extent of their similarity and differences. Five regions under study were located in different geographical belts and climate zones and, thus, provide an insight into socio-economic circumstances in completely different regions of the Russian Empire (see Appendix Table A1).

In previous papers on social and economic development of the Russian Empire, scholars mostly used data on provinces only in the European part. It is very rare to find statistics on non-European part of the Russian Empire (Markevich 2019) in some works. In this study we use data on two European provinces (the Novgorod and Simbirsk provinces) and three non-European regions (the Steppe region, Middle Asia and Far East). In the Steppe region, the budget surveys were conducted in two *oblasts* – Turgay and Urals – Table 2 provides data on these *oblasts* separately.

Even though the regions under study are located in completely different geographical, climate and soil zones with different population density, we can see similar institutional conditions in these regions, in particular, a low level of urbanization, community-based organization of peasant households, and a high percentage of allotments in communal ownership.

The table shows that the Amur *oblast* was the most developed among the studied regions, with higher levels of urbanization and population literacy and a higher labor productivity in agriculture. Specific features of the Syr-Daria and Turgay *oblasts* include settlers from European regions of Russia as well as a wider ethnic diversity, whereas the local population was mostly involved in cattle breeding, while Russian settlers were more focused on land farming. The two provinces of European Russia differ significantly in their agricultural conditions. The Simbirsk province has rather fertile lands and was among the provinces exporting grain, in contrast, the soil in the Novgorod province is poor and the province had to import grain, and peasants earned their income through seasonal work.

Despite serious differences, the main institutions predetermining agriculture were the community and communal lands. The percentage of privately-owned peasant lands was low not only in these regions but throughout Russia. Out of the fifty provinces of European Russia, only in eleven the percentage of land in private ownership exceeded 50%. In nine out of these eleven provinces, most of the privately-owned land belonged to the gentry, and the share of peasant land in private ownership hardly exceeded 10%. Only in two provinces (the Taurian and Pskov *oblasts*) a significant share of land in private ownership – over 30% – belonged to peasants (Rozinskaya et al. 2021).

It was the responsibility of the *zemstvo* (district council) to collect budget data, including those we have used. They gathered information from voluntary contributors. Local governments published collections of data aggregated at the province and district levels, as well as microdata based on the rural population census.

There were two types of territorial censuses. 1. Household censuses, which were comprehensive censuses, and the results were presented in tables organized by peasant groups either by the amount of land or by the number of horses. 2. Budget surveys where certain households were selected for a more detailed description. The selection could be either mechanical, every 20th or 10th household, or typological, where typical households were selected. The budget surveys in the late 19th century revealed some disadvantages of the mechanical selection, and the XI Assembly of Naturalists and Doctors in 1901 elaborated certain criteria for typical households and methods of their selection (Proceedings of the Statistics Subsection... 1902, p. 374). Subsequent censuses followed this methodology.

Based on data from household censuses, a sample of households for budget surveys was selected to ensure that representatives of all economic groups were included in the list proportionally to the size of each group. That is, the total budget of the selected households was intended to represent a smaller model of the total household income in the region: all medium and relative sizes of the two totals were intended to match, while all absolute values of the budget total multiplied by the sample rate were intended to provide total figures for the aggregate household income of the entire region (Chayanov 1989, p. 47). Since the censuses were carried out by distinguished territorial statisticians of the time, we can conclude that the data they collected were quite reliable.

Analysis of the level of peasant household technological development

In the countries where the agricultural revolution had been completed by the late 19th century, the main characteristics that encouraged the start of the modernization process were as follows: adaptation of new crops such as flax and potatoes, use of fertilizers, development

of cattle breeding, increase in mechanization and capital-labor ratio. It would be interesting to have a look at the same characteristics in the regions under study (Table 2).

The main characteristics showing the start of the modernization process are at a very low level. Compared to other regions, the most advanced is the Amur *oblast*. However, even in this region, which was already using green fodder, the number of cattle per farm was low. So, we cannot consider such an important characteristic of modernization as the integration of cattle breeding and grain growing. Unfortunately, there is little data available on the use of fertilizers, however, based on crop yields, it seems that they were not much used.

To identify the factors that influence the production process we analyzed the production function. First, we regressed the logarithmic Cobb-Douglas production function (Table 3). Then, we evaluated the following production function:

$$\ln(Y_i) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \ln(K_i) + \beta_3 \ln(L_i) + \beta_4 \ln(S_i) + \varepsilon_i$$

where Y_i – harvest of main grain crop, K_i – area under crop, L_i – number of workers, S_i – number of horses.

Table 2. Technological development of households in the regions under study

	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	Governor-Generalship of the Steppes	The Syr-Darya region	The Amur region
Grass planting (percentage)	4.1	NA	NA	0.01	19 (fallow)
Use of fertilizers per hectare	1.98	NA	NA	NA	NA
Capital ratio (average ratio of equipment cost to family working forces)	4.33	7.38	39.75	6.03	87.14
Mechanization (average cost of equipment)	14.86	59.69	226.26	34.97	309.45
Cattle breeding (average number of livestock per farm)	4.67	3.24	4.85	5.87	6.43
Average arable area per farm	11.8	11.35	11.065	14.64	24.8
Level of literacy in population	0.41	0.53	0.41	0.11	0.38
Marketability	0.31	NA	0.33	0.37	0.37
Share of earnings outside the agricultural sector	0.47	0.54	0.38	0.07	0.43
Share of communal lands	0.90	0.64	0.78	0.97	0.96
Share of wage labor	NA	0.14	NA	0.09	0.36
Share of rented land	0.34	0.69	0.33	0.04	0.03
Share of families with less than 6 members	0.90	0.79	0.27	0.60	0.98
Average technical efficiency (c)	0.66	0.63	0.69	0.67	0.52

	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	Governor-Generalship of the Steppes	The Syr-Darya region	The Amur region
Sown area per man	1.43	4.70	2.66	2.14	6.98
Yield (production per hectare)	65.57	22.30	26.45	44.78	17.09
Share of income on food	41	15	38	66	35
Share of income on clothing	16	18	15	20	10
Share of income per household	31	48	45	11	54
Share of income on spiritual needs	7	0.4	NA	0.9	NA

Sources: Glavnoe upravlenie zemleustroistva i sel'skogo khozyaistva, otdel pereseleniya. Dannye byudzhethno-hozyajstvennogo obsledovaniya 75-ti Pereselencheskih hozyajstv Kustanajnskogo, Aktyubinskogo i Ural'skogo uezdov [Main Department of Land Management and Agriculture, Relocation department. Data from budgetary and economic monitoring of 75 resettlement farms of the Kustanai, Aktobe and Uralsk districts] (1911) Izdanie Turgajsko-Ural'skoj pereselencheskoj organizacii; Izvestiya Amurskoi ehkspeditsii, poslannye po vysochaischemu komandovaniyu; vypusk 2. Materialy statistiko-ekonomicheskogo obsledovaniya kazach'ego i krest'yanskogo hozyajstva Amurskoj oblasti [Proceedings of the Amur Expedition sent by the highest command; issue 2. Materials of statistical and economic research of Cossack and peasant economy of the Amur region] (1913) St. Petersburg; Glavnoe upravlenie zemleustroistva i sel'skogo khozyaistva. Otdel pereezda. Hozyajstvennyj byt kirgizskogo, sartovskogo i russkogo naseleniya yugo-vostochnoj chasti Chimkentskogo uezda Syr-Dar'inskoy oblasti: dannye byudzhethnogo issledovaniya [Main Department of Land Management and Agriculture. Relocation department. Household life of the Kyrgyz, Sart and Russian population of the south-eastern part of the Chimkent district of the Syr-Darya region: data from a budgetary study] (1910) Tashkent; Raschetno-statisticheskii otdel Novgorodskoi gubernskoi zemskoi upravly. Byudzhety krest'yanskikh hozyajstv Novgorodskoj gubernii [Estimation and statistical department of the Novgorod province Zemstvo council. Budgets of peasant farms of Novgorod province] (1918) Gubernskaya tipografiya. Novgorod; Kratkie byudzhethnye svedeniya po hutorskomu i obshchinnomu krest'yanskomu hozyajstvu Simbirskoj gubernii [Brief budgetary information on the farm and communal peasant economy of the Simbirsk province] (1914) Simbirsk.

Table 3. Results of the production function regression

	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	Governor-Generalship of the Steppes	The Syr-Darya region	The Amur region
Log(crops)	0.66**	0.46***	0.83***	0.90***	0.65***
Log (number of workers)	0.20	0.14	-0.07	-0.02	0.18
Log (number of horses)	0.36*	0.41***	0.22	-0.17	0.41*
Intercept	3.07***	4.71***	3.45***	3.85***	2.64***
R^2	0.51	0.44	0.81	0.68	0.57
Number of observations	90	222	65	89	54

Source: Obtained by the authors.

The table shows that the following two main factors had the highest impact on the output: the amount of land and the number of horses, whereas, the number of workers turned out to be insignificant. Comparing these data with European figures provided by Van Zanden, we can see that the main difference is related to the workforce factor, which, according to European data, had the biggest impact: the level of total productivity was measured on the basis of the Cobb-Douglas production function, that assigned weights of 0.35, 0.50, and 0.15 to land, labor, and livestock, respectively. These weights are based on research by Bublout, *La Production*, p. 32-3, and Van Zanden, *Economische ontwikkeling*, p. 125” (Van Zanden 1991, p. 219).

Here, as the factor “number of workers” proved to be insignificant, therefore, the stochastic frontier model was used, which, in the case of a wider dispersion within the sample, provides a more reliable result.

The stochastic frontier model is as follows. The observed amount Y_i of the function for the output of i peasant household is presented as a production of a potential output Y_i^0 and index c_i , which ranges between 0 and 1.

$$Y_i = Y_i^0 \cdot c_i.$$

Index c_i is called technical efficiency and is interpreted as the index of using the available capacities. Accordingly, in the logarithmic form an additional term $u_i = \ln(c_i)$, which can have only negative values, is added to the equation.

$$\ln Y_i = \beta^0 + \beta^1 \ln(X_i^1) + \dots + \beta^k \ln(X_i^k) + \varepsilon_i + u_i.$$

This additional term u_i , as well as ε_i is interpreted as a random variable. The model is evaluated by the maximum likelihood method, then the estimated value \hat{u}_i is found, and the estimated technical efficiency value \hat{u}_i is also found.

An important question is whether \hat{u}_i is a constant value or not. Substantially, it is about whether the index of using the available capacities is constant across different households.

So, if \hat{u}_i is constant, it means that all households equally use the available capacities. The model is estimated by the maximum likelihood method. For this purpose, it was assumed that errors ε_i are independent and have an equal normal distribution with zero mean, and u_i are independent of each other, independent of ε_i and have the same normal distribution cut to zero. Below are the results of the evaluation.

We can see that the dispersion \hat{u}_i for all models, except for the third one, is significantly different from zero (parameter σ^2 is significant at 5% for all models, except for the third one), that is, both \hat{u}_i , and, accordingly, c_i – are not constant. Therefore, all the households in the study used the available capacities differently in terms of the effective use of available resources (some used more efficiently, some – less). That means, that the relationship between output and resources is more complex than what a linear regression can capture. Therefore, the stochastic frontier model is more appropriate than a simple log-linear model in all cases, except for the provinces of the Governor-Generalship of the Steppes.

It is the arable area that turns out to be a major factor in the stochastic frontier model, as well as in the traditional log-linear model. The factor “number of horses” (ranks second) proved to be insignificant, while “cost of equipment” became the second important factor. It is worth mentioning that when the factor “cost of equipment” was added to the model, the factor “number of workers” didn’t become more significant. It is consistent with the

findings of I. Kovalchenko's analysis of peasant budgets in the Penza province (Kovalchenko et al. 1988, p. 92). The analysis results show that, in order to make better use of the available capacities, a worker needed either horses or equipment.

Table 4. Results of the stochastic frontier model estimation

	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	Governor-Generalship of the Steppes	The Syr-Darya region	The Amur region
Log(equipment cost)	0.23	0.33***	0.15***	-0.04	0.17
Log(crops)	0.59**	0.36***	0.80***	0.92***	0.72***
Log(number of workers)	0.01	0.17***	-0.06	0.10	0.10
Intercept	3.38***	3.93***	3.37***	4.02***	3.26***
sigmaSq	0.36**	0.58***	0.34	0.39***	1.08***
Average technical efficiency (c)	0.66	0.63	0.69	0.67	0.52
Number of observations	29	224	62	67	51

Source: Obtained by the authors. Note: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' ' ' 1

The model also proves that, despite certain differences in the efficiency of using resources among households, there are no significant technological differences across the regions. The model demonstrates that management of households was extensive, as it is impossible to increase output by simply increasing the number of equipment/horses. In this aspect the conclusions are in line with Gregory Clark's findings regarding the low efficiency of peasant households in Russia. He proved that output per agricultural worker in Northern states of the U.S. and Great Britain in the early 19th century was much higher than in Eastern Europe, including Russia (Clark 1987). Additionally, the results obtained support the conclusions made by Leonard C.S., who used more aggregated data (Leonard 2011).

Marketability of households

Despite technological characteristics, another major indicator of modernization in the agricultural sector is the level of its integration into market relations. To evaluate this level among peasant households in the studied regions we calculated several indicators characterizing goods-money relations (Table 2).

The table shows that marketability in all regions under study ranged between 31-37%, which means that two-thirds of the goods produced by peasant households was self-consumed, and only one-third was sold in the market. This indicates a low level of household integration into market relations. The level of income from non-agricultural activities is higher in areas with more fertile soil. This suggests that market relations emerge only when agricultural resources are missing. A low level of literacy and a high percentage of allotments in communal ownership show that peasant households remained within the framework of a traditional society.

Efficiency of households

Another important factor of the agricultural revolution is the growth of efficiency in agriculture. Table 2 shows all major indicators characterizing various aspects of peasant household efficiency.

There are several variables, that can be considered as indicators of peasant household efficiency: technical efficiency as measured by the stochastic frontier model, yield of the main grain crop (either rye or wheat), and sown area per man. To reveal the main determinants of efficiency as factors influencing the selected indicator of efficiency, we first examined variables, characterizing household infrastructure (number of workers, number of horses, cost of equipment, and cost of buildings per hectare), and second, variables characterizing the level of household modernization (marketability of income, share of household literate members, share of rented land), and third, variables characterizing the household size (crop of wheat/rye, cost of equipment without normalization).

The tables below present the regression evaluation results. In order to avoid including insignificant variables in the tables, we excluded them if they did not result in a pathological behavior (a variable that is significant in a longer model, becomes insignificant in a shorter one).

Table 5. Results of the regression analysis

The dependent variable is the efficiency indicator from the stochastic frontier model					
	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	Governor-Generalship of the Steppes	The Syr-Darya region	The Amur region
Wheat/rye yield	0.01***	1.52e-02***	3.05e-04***	0.0003***	3.58e-04***
Cost of equipment	-0.01***	-1.1e-04.	-2.94e-04**	-0.001***	-2.75e-04**
Intercept	0.50***	5.9e-01**	6.75e-01***	0.61***	4.59e-01***
Number of observations	29	224	62	67	51

Source: Obtained by the authors

Table 6. Results of the regression analysis

The dependent variable is the sown area per man					
	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	Governor-Generalship of the Steppes	The Syr-Darya region	The Amur region
Share of literate members	-0.07	2.56**	-0.77	2.49**	15.58
Marketability of income	-0.14	5.35***	-0.05	-2.15	15.96*
Intercept	0.05**	0.31	2.84***	1.92**	-7.21
Number of observations	89	224	72	72	73

Source: Obtained by the authors

Table 7. Results of the regression analysis

The dependent variable is the rye/wheat yield					
	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	Governor-Generalship of the Steppes	The Syr-Darya region	The Amur region
Marketability of income	3.66 [*]	NA	0.003.	29.28.	NA
Cost of non-residential buildings	0.002	NA	0.003	NA	NA
Number of horses	NA	167.12 ^{***}	NA	NA	15.28 ^{***}
Cost of equipment	NA	NA	NA	1.03 ^{**}	NA
Share of literate members	NA	NA	0.36	20.05 [*]	NA
Share of rented land	NA	NA	-0.17 ^{**}	NA	NA
Share of allotment land	NA	NA	0.20	NA	NA
Intercept	4.32	1.23	1.36	25.76	3.64
Number of observations	89	218	63	94	73

Source: Obtained by the authors

The table describing the results of evaluating the model, where the yield of wheat was used as a dependent variable, contains gaps. A gap means that the variable in question was insignificant, and it was removed from the model, while other model coefficients did not show any abnormal behavior.

The analysis demonstrates that besides the size of the household (area of cultivated land) and equipment cost, such factors as the share of literate members and household marketability also had an impact on efficiency. It is interesting to mention that only in the Simbirsk province the number of horses proved to be a significant factor. Considering that equipment cost turned out to be insignificant in the Simbirsk province, one can conclude that machines were less used in this region than in other regions, as the demand for horses diminishes when machines are used.

To provide the same level of production, poorer households had to use more labor, that is, to increase their labor intensity.

The structure of consumption in households

One possible explanation of the fact, why Russian peasants shifted so slowly to market relations may be that Russia during the period under study had not yet undergone the Industrious Revolution. The term “Industrious revolution” was introduced by de Vries to explain increasing commercialization of the agricultural sector in England (De Vries 1994). By industrious revolution he meant a sharp increase in labor intensity, driven by the desire to consume more and more various products. The structure of peasant households in the regions under study is shown in Table 2.

From the table, we can see that at the beginning of the 20th century, the majority of income was spent on household needs and food (Table 2), while in the UK, in the late 19th

century, only about 30% of the household income was spent on food with the rest going towards household items, clothing, houseware, furniture, books, etc. (De Vries 2016, p. 155). The survey on different regions of Russia shows that proximity to big cities has contributed to a higher demand for various goods among households in Russia as well. Thus, for example, in research on central industrial regions we see growing expenditures on various household items and luxury goods. The work emphasizes that "... emerging "consumer culture" was evident in rural areas, especially in districts like Iur'ev and Rostov where there was a substantial amount of migratory labor to Moscow and Petersburg. According to rural worker and peasant budgets from Vladimir, Iaroslavl', and the rest of European Russia, grain and other foodstuffs took up 40-70% of household expenditures, while clothing constituted another 5-15 percent. A further 10-20 percent went towards livestock expenses, leaving 15-40 percent for housing, non-essentials, and luxury goods." (Dennison and Nafziger 2011, p. 11). These figures show that even in the regions close to major cities, food products made up the biggest part of the budget. Besides, from these data we can see how little from peasant budgets was allocated to education and spiritual needs, which is no wonder considering such a low level of literacy in population. Peasant households in the regions studied, like most households in Russia at that time, continued to produce goods for the market in very limited quantities, even though the assortment of food products had considerably expanded by the early 20th century. According to de Vries, households had two main ways to increase their monetary income through integrating into market relations – either specialization or protoindustrial production (de Vries 2016, p. 126). If we look at the indicators in Tables 5-7, we see that households in the Simbirsk province tend to follow the first way, that is to specialize in grain production, while in the Novgorod province and in the Amur *oblast* there is an obvious trend towards protoindustrial production. However, these potential future benefits, which a household was only counting on so far, were offset by high current operational costs. People who got used to alternate work and rest depending on daylight hours, to the rhythm of seasonal work and successive periods of intense work and idleness, had to adapt to the discipline of systematic labor (De Vries 2016, p. 189).

Conclusions

The system analysis of peasant budgets and specifics of their formation allows us to draw qualitative and quantitative conclusions about the economic situation of the main production unit of the agricultural sector, as well as to evaluate the level of market relation development in agriculture in the early 20th century.

The analysis of the productive function showed that the main factors that had a considerable impact on the output were the amount of land and the number of horses, while the number of workers proved to be insignificant. The stochastic frontier model further suggests that there were no significant technological differences across regions, while the technologies used did not differ much from the ones employed in previous centuries.

The study of peasant households aimed to understand how integrated they were into market relations. The results demonstrated that marketability ranged between 31% to 37% in all regions under study, meaning that two-thirds of the produced goods was consumed by the households themselves, and only one-third was sold in the market. This confirms the low level of household integration into market relations. The share of profit outside agricultural activities is high in areas with less fertile soil, indicating that market relations emerge

only when there is a lack of resources from agricultural production. The low literacy level and high share of allotment land in communal ownership suggest that peasant households remained within the framework of a traditional society.

The analysis of the determinants of peasant household efficiency showed that, besides the size of the household (cultivated land) and equipment costs, other factors as the share of literate members and the household marketability also had an impact on efficiency. It is also worth mentioning that only in the Simbirsk province such a variable as the number of horses proved to be a significant factor. Considering that the factor of equipment costs was found to be insignificant for the Simbirsk province, we can conclude that in this region they used less machinery than in other provinces, as the need for horses reduces when machines are used.

Thus, the analysis of technical and economic factors demonstrates that the key indicators of the start of the mechanization process are at an extremely low level. When comparing with other regions, the Amur *oblast* is the most developed based on these indicators. However, even in this *oblast*, where green fodder (seed herbs) was already being used, the number of cattle per farm was still low. This means that we cannot consider the integration of cattle breeding and grain growing to be an important indicator of modernization.

The study of the consumption pattern showed that, in Russia, in the early 20th century, most of the income was spent on household needs and food. Furthermore, based on the data, we can see how little from the peasant budget was allocated to education and spiritual needs. This is no surprise, given the low level of literacy in population at that time.

We can conclude that in Russia during the period under study, the modernization of the agricultural sector was at an early stage, as the processes that could later result in the agricultural revolution had just begun.

Considering that in the 1920s, Russian statisticians continued to conduct budget surveys, it would be interesting in future to compare the level of modernization of peasant households in the pre-revolutionary period with that of the late 1920s, on the eve of collectivization. In addition, an international comparison would be of great interest. It would be also interesting to analyze how similar Russian peasant households and peasant households in other countries were; and which period of social and economic development in Western European countries corresponded to the level of Russian peasant households in the pre-revolutionary period.

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Appendix

Table A1. Comparative characteristics of the regions under study

	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	The Turgay oblast	The Ural oblast ¹	The Syr-Darya region	The Amur region
Area in square versts (1 verst = 1.07 km)	104 163.4	43 491	418 138	284 412	458 793	394 969,6
Total population	1 356 702	1 750 600	453 416 (1987) 712615 (1910)	645 429 (1897) 804 245 (1910)	1 796 655 (1909)	286263 (1910)
Level of literacy in population ²	23%	15.6% (1910)	4.5% (1897) for men, 1.2% for women)	12.4% ³ (1897)	Entire population – 5%, Russian immigrants – 26% (1897)	54.5% ⁴
Population density (people/verst)	13	40.3	1.7	2.8	4.0	0.8
Share of rural population (%)	91	92	95.7	91	84.7	76
Share of male population (%)	651901	48%	376673 (1911) 51.5%	422 813 (1910) 52.3%	970 237 (1909) 54%	172240 (1910)
Real gross regional product per capita in 1897 (in the 1897 rubles)	50-55	<50	<50	70-80	55-60	125-150
Gross value added per capita in 1897 (in the 1897 rubles)	5-10	5-10	<5	<5	5-10	40-50
Labor productivity in agriculture in 1897 (in the 1897 rubles)	55-60	55-60	<50	90-100	80-90	>150
Share of communal (nadel'nye) land (%) ⁵	83.6 (1916)	80.3 (1916)	96 (1910)	98 (1910)	94 (1909)	97 (1912)

	The Novgorod province	The Simbirsk province	The Turgay oblast	The Ural oblast¹	The Syr- Darya region	The Amur region
Approximate % of serfs in 1859) (of the total popu- lation) ⁶	45.07 (418855 people)	58,83 (442455 people)	No serfdom	No serfdom	No serfdom	No serfdom

Sources: **The Amur region:** Obzor Amurskoj oblasti za 1910 god. Prilozhenie k vsepoddanneishemu otchetu Voennogo gubernatora Amurskoj oblasti [Review of the Amur Region for 1910. Addendum to the Most Submissive Report of the Military Governor of the Amur Region] (1911) Izdanie Amurskij oblastnoj statisticheskij komitet. Obzor Amurskoj oblasti za 1912 god. Prilozhenie k vsepoddanneishemu otchetu Voennogo gubernatora Amurskoj oblasti [Review of the Amur Region for 1912. Addendum to the Most Submissive Report of the Military Governor of the Amur Region] (1913) Izdanie Amurskij oblastnoj statisticheskij komitet. **The Syr-Darya region:** Obzor Syr-Dar'inskoj oblasti za 1909 god [Review of the Syr-Darya region for 1909] (1911) Tipografiya pri kancelyarii Turkest. Tashkent. **The Ural region:** Obzor Ural'skoj obl. za 1910 god. Prilozhenie k vsepoddanneishemu otchetu Voennogo gubernatora [Review of the Ural region for 1910. Addendum to the Most Submissive Report of the Military Governor] (1911) Ural'sk. **The Turgay region:** Obzor Turgajskoj obl. za 1910 god. Prilozhenie k vsepoddanneishemu otchetu Voennogo gubernatora [Review of the Turgay region for 1910. Addendum to the Most Submissive Report of the Military Governor] (1911) Orenburg. **The Novgorod province:** Obzor Novgorodskoj gubernii za 1911 god. [Review of the Novgorod province for 1911] (1912) Novgorod; Statisticheskij spravochnik po agrarnomu voprosu [Statistical Handbook on the Agrarian Question] Pod. red. Oganovskogo NP, Chayanova AV, vypusk 1 [Oganovsky NP, Chayanov AV (Eds), issue 1] (1917) Moskva, «Universal'naya biblioteka». **The Simbirsk province:** Statisticheskij obzor Simbirskoj gubernii za 1911 god. [Statistical review of the Simbirsk province for 1911] (1912) Simbirsk; Statisticheskij spravochnik po agrarnomu voprosu [Statistical Handbook on the Agrarian Question] Pod. red. Oganovskogo NP, Chayanova AV, vypusk 1 [Oganovsky NP, Chayanov AV (Eds), issue 1] (1917) Moskva, «Universal'naya biblioteka»; Markevich A (2019) Regional Perspective on the Economic Development of the late Russian Empire, May 14. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2555273> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2555273>. *Примечания:* ¹ The Ural and Turgay regions were part of the Governor-Generalship of the Steppes. ² Rashin AG (1956) Naselenie Rossii za 100 let (1813-1913) Statisticheskie ocherki, tabl.242 [Statistical essays, table. 242]. ³ Kessler G, Markevich (2019) Electronic Repository of Russian Historical Statistics, 18th – 21st centuries: <https://ristat.org>. ⁴ Istoriya razvitiya gosudarstvennoj statistiki v Amurskoj oblasti 1895-2015 [History of the development of state statistics in the Amur region 1895-2015] (2015) Davydova GA (Ed). ⁵ Ministerstvo Zemledeliya (Komitet po Zemleustroitel'nym Delam). Kratkij ocherk za desyatiletie 1906-1916 (1916) Petrograd. ⁶ Trojnickij AG (1861) Krepostnoe naselenie v Rossii po 10-j narodnoj perezpisi: statisticheskoe issledovanie, 58.